

Optimality Criteria for Fuzzy Pseudo Convex Functions

Authors : S. K. Behera, J. R. Nayak

Abstract : In convex optimization we can get both global and local solutions to different classes of problems. Non convex models pose a greater challenge to find global optimal solutions. In practical field the optimization models are mostly nonlinear and non convex in nature. In this paper we have considered non convex programming problems for which the optimality criteria are proposed. The objective function is assumed to be fuzzy pseudo convex. The constraints and the variables are considered in the fuzzy domain

Keywords : Fuzzy pseudo convex functions, fuzzy quasi convex functions, fuzzy triangular numbers, non convex programming problem

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014